

MS time course experiment for GS loop mutations.

An MS time course assay was used to monitor the ability of ALK2 GS loop mutations to phosphorylate SMAD1 compared to the wild type.

Mutations used:

Construct ID (Construct)	Construct Protein Sequence (Construct)
ACVR1Z-c103	SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHACTSGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQ
ACVR1Z-c104	SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHSCASGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQ
ACVR1Z-c105	SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHACASGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQ
ACVR1Z-c106	SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHSCTAGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQ
ACVR1Z-c108	SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHSCTSGSGAGLPFLVQRTVARQ
ACVR1Z-c109	SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHSCTAGAGSGLPFLVQRTVARQ
ACVR1Z-c110	SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHSCTAGSGAGLPFLVQRTVARQ
ACVR1Z-c113	SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHACAAGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQ

Table showing GS loop mutations in constructs used for the assay

Proteins were thawed from storage at -80°C and concentrations assessed by Nano drop.

From the concentrations, appropriate dilutions were calculated to get a final concentration of 60 µM for all receptor proteins in a reaction mix of 100 µL (volume made up with water). SMAD1 was used

A 'master mix' containing ATP (0.5mM), ions (Mg²⁺ at 5mM /Mn²⁺ at 2mM) and DTT (5mM) was made up and added to activate the reaction at the start of the experiment.

	Absorbance	Extinction coefficient	Concentration uM	volume for 100ul rx at 60uM
ACVR1 WT	10.6	58900	179.9660441	33.33962264
ACVR1 103	12.4	58900	210.5263158	28.5
ACVR1 104	26.7	58900	453.3106961	13.23595506
ACVR1 105	15.02	58900	255.008489	23.5286285
ACVR1 106	13.6	58900	230.8998302	25.98529412
ACVR1 108	5.08	58900	86.24787776	69.56692913
ACVR1 109	23.2	58900	393.8879457	15.23275862
ACVR1 110	13.5	58900	229.2020374	26.17777778
ACVR1 113	8.85	58900	150.2546689	39.93220339
ACVR2A	19.55	51900	376.6859345	15.92838875
SMAD1	4.7	35410	132.730867	30.13617021

Measured concentrations of proteins by nanodrop.

Reactions were set up in a 96 well plate, the plate was spun to ensure thorough mixing before the reaction was started by the addition of 8 µL of master mix. 1 µL of reaction mixture was extracted from each experimental condition simultaneously using a multi-channel pipette at specific time

points (0min, 5min, 30min, 1h and 2h) and the reaction quenched with acid in 60 μ L Mass Spec running buffer (water with 0.1% formic acid).

Mass spec analysis:

Intact mass was determined using a QTOF mass spectrometer. A C3 cartridge was used for HPLC prior to ionisation.

The resulting chromatogram was used to extract the appropriate spectra corresponding to protein elution peak from the C3 column. All spectra were extracted simultaneously. Deconvolution was undertaken between 10kDa and 50kDa across a limited m/z range of 600 – 3000.

Data was exported with a peak intensity for every Dalton of the deconvoluted spectra. The data was plotted using Excel for the 2h time point only in the first instance. This was shown to be sufficient to see differences between the constructs

The complete set of data can be found in the Zenodo Excel file.

Phosphorylation on SMAD1

Phosphorylation on ALK2

Summary figures showing the phosphorylation of SMAD1 and ALK2 using various ALK2 GS loop mutants. The top row on both columns shows the wild type positive control for comparison. The constructs are then ranked from least to most effected moving down the first column (with matching SMAD1 and ALK2 traces) and then down the second column.

The constructs in the figure above have been ranked according to severity of effect on the phosphorylation of SMAD1 compared to the wild type (which shows no unphosphorylated SMAD and predominantly species containing one and two phosphorylation events.). In cases where SMAD phosphorylation was equally effected, the effect on the phosphorylation of ALK2 was used to rank the constructs.

The three constructs most effected were c109, c106 and c113 showing nearly no activity. Construct c105 showed minimal single phosphorylation of SMAD1 and so is also considered here.

ACVR1Z-c105	SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHACASGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQ
ACVR1Z-c109	SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHSCTAGAGSGLPFLVQRTVARQ
ACVR1Z-c106	SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHSCTAGSGLPFLVQRTVARQ
ACVR1Z-c113	SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHACAAGSGLPFLVQRTVARQ

When their mutations are aligned we can see that the three constructs that abrogate activity entirely all contain a mutation at the N terminal end of the GSGGS section of the GS loop. Equally c105 contains a mutation only one residue away from that which might explain the observed results.